

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: PULLAT****FIRST NAME: FAZALUL RAHIMAN****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the exact information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

The plagiarism rate in this paper (per Grammarly Premium) is: 4%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2021 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which of the following is true to American and British English? ¹
 - They are variants of World English.
 - They are more similar than different.
 - Their difference is related to national histories and cultural development.
 - All of the above.**

2. Among the following, which one does not come under plagiarism?²
 - Use the words of a source without giving quotation marks.
 - Take ideas from a source without providing a footnote.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 25.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 14.

- Cite the author or source when using information.**
- All of the above.
3. Which of the following best suits Pure Research, Applied Research, and Hypothesis?³
- Pure research addresses a conceptual problem with no direct practical consequence; Applied research addresses those with such a consequence; a Hypothesis is a tentative or speculative answer to a research question.**
- Pure research addresses a conceptual problem with direct practical consequence; Applied research addresses those which does not have such a consequence; a Hypothesis is a proven answer to a research question.
- Pure research addresses a practical problem with direct conceptual consequence; Applied research addresses those which does have such a consequence; a Hypothesis is a proven answer to a research question.
- Pure research addresses a fictitious problem with indirect conceptual consequence; Applied research addresses those with such a consequence; a Hypothesis is a partially proven answer to a research question.
4. Which of the following are the essential elements of an *Argument*?⁴
- Claim, reason, evidence, acknowledgment and response, and warrant.**
- Claim, reason, evidence, acknowledgment and question, and warrant.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago; London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 29 &30.

⁴ Turabian, 58.

- Claim, reason, evidence, assumption and response, and warrant.
 - Claim, objective, evidence, acknowledgment and response, and warrant.
5. Among the following, which one states the correct difference between the Notes-Bibliography Style and the Author-Date Style of the Turabian source of citations?⁵
- Notes-Bibliography Style is citing of sources in superscript numbered footnotes or endnotes, and Author-Date Style is citing of sources in detail in the text, usually in parentheses, by the author's last name and year of publication
 - Notes-Bibliography Style is citing sources in superscript numbered footnotes or endnotes. Author-Date Style cites sources briefly in the text, usually in parentheses, by the author's first name and year of publication.
 - Notes-Bibliography Style is citing sources in superscript numbered footnotes or endnotes. Author-Date Style cites sources briefly in the text, usually in parentheses, by the author's last name and year of publication.**
 - Notes-Bibliography Style is citing sources in subscript-numbered footnotes or endnotes. Author-Date Style cites sources briefly in the text, usually in parentheses, by the author's last name and year of publication.
6. What is the difference between Selected Bibliography and Annotated Bibliography?⁶
- Only some citations are present in Selected Bibliography, whereas Annotated Bibliography is a complete description of sources.

⁵ Turabian, 142.

⁶ Turabian, 155.

- Only some authors' names are present in Selected Bibliography, whereas a source description is present in Annotated Bibliography.
- Only some citations are present in Selected Bibliography, whereas Annotated Bibliography is a list of authors' names.
- Only some citations are present in Selected Bibliography, whereas a source description is present in Annotated Bibliography.**

7. Which of the following are the research paradigms?⁷

- Ontology, epistemology, axiology, and phenomenology.
- Ontology, epistemology, axiology, and methodology.**
- Ontology, epistemology, ethnography, and methodology.
- Ontology, genres, axiology, and methodology.

8. Which of the following group represents the most common research methodologies?⁸

- Case study, hypothesis, phenomenology, grounded theory, narrative inquiry, action research, and critical genres.
- Case study, ethnography, phenomenology, grounded theory, narrative inquiry, dissertation, and critical genres.
- Case study, ethnography, phenomenology, grounded theory, narrative inquiry, action research, and critical genres.**

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (California: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019), 146.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 158.

- Case study, ethnography, phenomenology, grounded theory, narrative reporting, action research, and critical genres.

9. Which of the following is true in the case of verbs?⁹

- In time, the present perfect refers to situations or events in the period leading up to that time if writing from the present moment. Where the period's starting point is available, the present perfect is often used in its continuous form to emphasize the ongoing nature of the process. Use simple past if the reference is a time that ended before the present.
- In time, the present perfect refers to situations or events in the period leading up to that time if writing from the present moment. Where the period's starting point is available, the present perfect is often used in its continuous form to emphasize the ongoing nature of the process. Use simple past if the reference is a time that ended before the present.**
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- In time, the present perfect refers to situations or events in the period leading up to that time if writing from the present moment. Where the period's starting point is

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 8th ed. (Brussels: European Commission, 2021), 55.

available, the present perfect is often used in its continuous form to emphasize the ongoing nature of the process. Use a simple present if the reference is a time that ended before the present.

10. Which of the following is true in the case of nouns?¹⁰

- Collective nouns take the singular where the emphasis is on the whole entity. Sums of money can be a singular or plural verb, while the percentages and fractions of countable nouns take a singular verb. When referring to countable items, take the plural. Countries and organizations with a plural name take the singular.
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¹⁰ European Commission, 53.

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